

Spatial concentration of Research and Innovation funding: How do excellence and cohesion logics differ?

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**Spatial concentration of Research and Innovation funding:
How do excellence and cohesion logics differ at the sub-regional level?**

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Abstract

This paper examines the spatial distribution of European Union research and innovation (R&I) funding, comparing excellence-oriented (Horizon 2020) and cohesion-oriented (Cohesion Policy) instruments, and analysing the role of governance level within Cohesion Policy. Using NUTS3-level data from the 2014-2020 programming period and spatial econometric models, we find that Horizon 2020 funding is concentrated in regions with high patent intensity, GDP per capita, and knowledge-intensive services, reinforcing cumulative advantage and contributing predominantly to within-country inequalities in access to funding. Cohesion R&I funding exhibits stronger between-country redistribution and integrates socio-economic vulnerability, though its internal allocation varies with governance: national management fosters clustering and positive spillovers, while regional management spreads resources more widely but intensifies intra-national competition. The results underscore the trade-offs inherent in EU R&I funding; policies that prioritise excellence, redistribution, or spatial coordination cannot maximise all objectives simultaneously, with governance choices mediating the balance between concentration, spillovers, and territorial equity.

Keywords: R&I funding; Cohesion Policy; Horizon 2020; Governance.

JEL Classification: O38, R58, R12, C21.

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1. Introduction

The main European Union (EU) funding instruments supporting Research and Innovation (R&I) are the Framework Programmes (FPs) for R&I (also called Horizon 2020 for 2014-2020 and Horizon Europe for 2021-2027) and the Cohesion policy (Conte & Santos, 2023). In the programming period 2021-2027, the budget allocated to Horizon Europe is EUR 93.5 billion, and to R&I under the Cohesion Policy¹ equivalent to EUR 29.5 billion. Both funds follow opposite intervention logics, with FP targeting excellence in science and centrally managed by the European Commission (EC), and Cohesion Policy aiming at capacity building and reduction of territorial inequalities, under shared-managed² between Member States and the EC (A. Santos & Conte, 2024). The different targets and management of funds may influence their territorial distribution (Molica & Marques Santos, 2024; Santos & Conte, 2024).

The spatial distribution of R&I funding in the European Union (EU) has long been characterized by a fundamental debate between the “excellence” and the “cohesion” rationale (Bachtrögler-Unger et al., 2025; Rubiera Morollón & Fernández García, 2023), and how this may impact the innovation divide across EU regions (Molica & Marques Santos, 2024).

Using data from the 2014-2020 programming period and spatial econometrics, this paper examines how socio-economic characteristics shape the sub-regional distribution of EU research and innovation funding under two distinct allocation logics: an excellence-based logic (Horizon 2020) and a cohesion-based logic (R&I Cohesion Policy). While Cohesion Policy formally allocates resources according to predefined regional eligibility criteria at NUTS2-level, existing evidence based on country-level case studies – Mieszkowski & Barbero (2021) for Poland; Santos and Conte (2024) for Portugal – suggests that, at higher regional disaggregation, the actual distribution of funds may not fully reflect this regulatory design. To investigate this issue, we estimate regression models in which per capita Horizon 2020 funding and per capita R&I Cohesion Policy funding are alternately used as dependent variables, explained by the same set of regional socio-economic indicators. Using the same sample of NUTS3 regions across all specifications allows for a direct comparison of how territorial characteristics influence the concentration of competitive versus cohesion-oriented funding. We further explore

¹ Information extracted from the Cohesion Open Data platform on 18/02/2026, referring to the planned EU contribution for the Specific Objective 1.1. - Enhancing research and innovation.

² Shared management means that the EC and the Member States jointly manage the funds. The EC sets rules and monitors, while Member States handle programming, implementation, and control.

heterogeneity in these relationships by estimating separate models for groups of regions defined by Cohesion Policy categories (more developed, transition, and less developed regions) and by broad geographical areas (Southern, Northern, Central, and Eastern Europe). Finally, we examine whether the governance model adopted by Member States (centralised versus decentralised management of R&I Cohesion Policy funds) is associated with different patterns of funding concentration, while holding constant the same set of explanatory variables.

This paper contributes to the literature on the geography of innovation (Asheim & Gertler, 2006; Feldman & Kogler, 2010) and on the spatial distribution of R&I funding (Dotti & Spithoven, 2018; Piro et al., 2024; A. Santos & Conte, 2024). It does so by developing, for the first time, a unified framework to assess the territorial characteristics associated with higher concentrations of R&I funding under different intervention logics. A clear gap in the literature motivates this analysis. While the “excellence logic” underpinning the Framework Programmes has been widely documented – see, for example, Dotti & Spithoven (2018); Piro et al. (2024) – far less attention has been paid to the territorial patterns associated with Cohesion Policy support for R&I at the sub-regional (NUTS-3) level. To address this gap, the paper examines the sub-regional distribution of Cohesion Policy funding through the lens of an excellence logic. This approach makes it possible to explore whether certain territorial characteristics are associated with higher concentrations of funding, including within countries where all regions are beneficiaries of convergence support, as suggested by Mieszkowski & Barbero (2021) for Poland.

2. Literature review

The relationship between excellence and cohesion has received increasing attention in the literature on European research and regional development policies. In recent years, greater emphasis on economic growth and innovation-driven competitiveness has become more visible within regional development strategies (Mendez, 2011; Molica et al., 2025). The emergence of mission-oriented policies has added an additional dimension to this debate, as the alignment between strategic directionality and territorial convergence goals remains an open question (Cappellano et al., 2024). In this context, regions are increasingly encouraged to identify complementarities between different funding instruments to strengthen their innovation capacity (Bachtrögler-Unger et al., 2025; Molica & Marques Santos, 2024).

Empirical research consistently highlights a deep spatial concentration of R&I funding. Participation in Framework Programmes, such as FP7 and Horizon 2020, remains heavily skewed toward a few core regions and institutions (Dotti & Spithoven, 2018; Piro et al., 2024). This concentration is often justified by the cumulative effects of R&D investments and the presence of high-quality innovation systems (Rodríguez-Pose & Crescenzi, 2008). However, scholars highlight the risk that such spatial concentration can reinforce regional disparities (Marques Santos et al., 2024; Molica & Marques Santos, 2024), effectively acting as a dark side of innovation geography, where relatedness and complexity advantages are captured by already advanced regions (Pinheiro et al., 2025). Fitjar (2025) argues that public R&D funding may unintentionally exacerbate these inequalities, as the excellence-logic naturally favours areas with pre-existing talent and infrastructure. This dynamic aligns with the concept of “Matthew effect” in science funding, whereby early success increases the probability of securing subsequent funding, generating self-reinforcing processes of cumulative advantage (Bol et al., 2018).

The introduction of Smart Specialization Strategies (S3), as *ex-ante* conditionality under the programming period 2014-2020 to access European Structural and Investment (ESI) Funds, aimed to provide a place-based framework for regions to identify their unique strengths (Ferreira et al., 2025). However, evidence suggests that S3 implementation has shown that many regions struggle to change established learning patterns, which makes it hard for less-developed regions to shift away from their traditional trajectories (Capello & Lenzi, 2016). In countries like Poland, territorial patterns of ESIF-funded R&D grants show a tendency to concentrate in NUTS-3 regions that already possess a degree of urban density and scientific infrastructure (Mieszkowski & Barbero, 2021). This suggests that even within the framework of Cohesion Policy, a concentration dynamic may emerge, with funding gravitating toward local centres of excellence located within broader lagging areas (A. Santos & Conte, 2024).

Lagging regions face multiple barriers to participating in excellence-driven networks. Institutional quality and governance play a critical role, especially when regions with lower government effectiveness often struggle to translate innovation policies into tangible results (Peiró-Palomino & Perugini, 2022). Furthermore, less advanced regions tend to play only a marginal role in high-tech innovation networks, where the barriers to entering the market are high (Calignano & Nordli, 2024). Although organisational and geographic diversity can increase the innovative potential of research networks (Nepelski et al., 2019), structural factors, such as business R&D expenditure and tertiary educational attainment, continue to constrain patenting activity in the lagging regions (Rodríguez-Pose

& Wilkie, 2019). Large-scale competitive university funding programs, while effective in strengthening scientific performance, often prioritise academic outputs over regional knowledge transfer, potentially limiting spillovers to local firms (Krieger, 2024).

While institutional quality is widely recognised as a driver of innovation performance (Peiró-Palomino & Perugini, 2022), a more specific and less explored issue concerns the level, national or regional, at which R&I funds are managed. The literature suggests that the location of policy management influences patterns of spatial allocation of funds (A. Santos & Conte, 2024). An emerging debate regarding whether national management is more closely aligned with an excellence-oriented logic than regional management has appeared in recent years (Bachtrögler-Unger et al., 2025; Dotti & Spithoven, 2018; Fitjar, 2025; Mendez, 2011; A. Santos & Conte, 2024). Evidence from Portugal provides a useful starting point for this discussion. Santos & Conte (2024) show that R&I funds managed at the national level display a territorial distribution that correlates much more strongly with the excellence-driven patterns observed under Horizon 2020 than funds managed by regional authorities. This finding suggests that national-level management may prioritise established scientific hubs to maximise aggregate performance, whereas regional authorities may be more responsive to local place-based needs (A. Santos & Conte, 2024). However, beyond specific case studies, the broader relationship between governance level and sub-regional (NUTS-3) outcomes remains insufficiently understood in innovation studies (Bachtrögler-Unger et al., 2025).

The existing literature has provided several robust evidence at the NUTS-2 level on the territorial distribution of funding (Dotti & Spithoven, 2018; Molica & Marques Santos, 2024; Piro et al., 2024), however, several areas are still underexplored. First, the predominance of NUTS-2 level analyses may mask significant disparities within regions. Only a limited number of recent studies examine NUTS-3 dynamics to understand how funding is allocated within lagging or transition regions (Bachtrögler-Unger et al., 2025; Mieszkowski & Barbero, 2021). Secondly, lagging regions are often treated as a homogenous group, overlooking the distinct socio-economic characteristics that differentiate disadvantaged territories (Rodríguez-Pose & Wilkie, 2019). Thirdly, most studies analyse Cohesion Policy as a single policy framework, without distinguishing between the spatial effects of nationally-managed and regionally-managed operational programs. This gap makes it difficult to determine whether a potential shift toward excellence within Cohesion Policy is primarily driven by national authorities or also takes shape at the regional level.

This paper addresses these issues by first assessing whether the 2014-2020 R&I Cohesion Policy funds at the sub-regional (NUTS3) level follow similar patterns to those observed under Horizon 2020, and then analysing differences in spatial allocation according to the governance framework. The study tests the hypothesis that nationally-managed R&I Cohesion Policy funds are more likely to display spatial concentration associated with an excellence-oriented logic, based on the work of Santos & Conte (2024) for Portugal.

3. Territorial distribution of R&I funding at the sub-regional level across the EU

The geographical distribution of R&I funds (Figure 1 and Figure 2) reveals a clear spatial divide between an excellence-driven logic and a cohesion-oriented one, creating two contrasting patterns of innovation across the European regions. Figure 1 shows that Horizon 2020 funding is concentrated in a limited number of highly performing NUTS-3 regions, creating a dispersed network of scientific excellence across Scandinavia, the Benelux area, and major metropolitan hubs such as Paris, Munich, and Madrid. Funding intensity suddenly declines outside these core areas, even within wealthy Member States. By contrast, Figure 2 indicates that R&I Cohesion Policy funding follows a predominantly compensatory pattern, reflecting its legislative design, with higher per capita allocations in Central and Eastern Europe and in parts of the Mediterranean. Rather than clustering in a minority of metropolitan areas, Cohesion Policy resources are more evenly distributed within national territories, particularly in countries classified as less developed, consistent with its compensatory allocation logic designed to support lagging regions (Table B1 in the Appendix). Indeed, this geographical distribution is shaped by the governance model of the funds. Horizon 2020 is centrally managed by the European Commission, with access to funds provided through competitive calls, whereas Cohesion Policy operates with a pre-allocated budget, directing larger amounts to less developed regions (Conte & Santos, 2023). Under this framework, some typologies of European regions tend to be more heavily dependent on the Cohesion Policy, as shown in Figure 3, whereas others can capture more than three times as competitive funds as less developed regions (Table B1 in the Appendix).

Figure 1. Horizon 2020 per capita

Figure 2. R&I Cohesion Policy per capita

Source: Own elaboration based on data from the European Commission’s Horizon dashboard (Figure 1) and Cohesion Open Data Platform (Figure 2) using 2014-2020 average population data from ARDECO [SNPTD].

Note: Value expressed in Purchasing Power Parity (PPS) and referring to the programming period 2014-2020.

Figure 3. Main source of R&I fundings

Figure 4. Governance model of R&I Cohesion Policy programs

Source: Own elaboration based on data from the European Commission’s Horizon dashboard (Figure 3) and Cohesion Open Data Platform (Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Note: Figure 3 reports the classification region as: mainly “Cohesion” if the ratio between R&I Cohesion Policy and Horizon 2020 is above 1.25, mainly “Horizon” if the ratio between R&I Cohesion Policy and Horizon 2020 is below 0.75; “Mix” if the ratio is between 0.75 and 1.25. For more info about the classification in Figure 4 see Appendix A.

Figure 3 clearly shows a Horizon-dominant core area emerging in Western and Northern Europe, while a Cohesion-dominant area characterises much of Eastern and Southern Europe. Regions where both instruments contribute in relatively balanced proportions (“Mix”) remain limited, suggesting that complementarities between excellence-driven and cohesion-oriented funding are not yet widespread at the sub-regional level. This finding resonates with recent discussions on the difficulty of achieving genuine synergies between EU instruments despite increasing policy emphasis on alignment (Bachtrögler-Unger et al., 2025; Molica & Marques Santos, 2024).

Figure 4 introduces an additional dimension, the governance level under which R&I Cohesion Policy funds are managed during the programming period 2014-2020. In less developed regions, the majority of R&I Cohesion Policy funding is channelled through National Operational Programmes (OP) – centralised management – whereas regional OPs – decentralised management – play a comparatively minor role (Table B1 in Appendix B). On average, per capita allocations managed at the national level are nearly double those managed regionally (Table B1 in Appendix B). This institutional configuration is particularly relevant in light of the emerging debate on whether national management is more prone to replicate excellence-oriented spatial patterns (Fitjar, 2025; A. Santos & Conte, 2024).

To complement this descriptive evidence, Table 1 reports Theil index values for Horizon 2020 and Cohesion R&I funding, both for the full sample and disaggregated by governance level of OPs within Cohesion Policy. The Theil index quantifies the inequality of per capita funding and decomposes total disparity into between-country and within-country components. Consistent with the previous maps, H2020 exhibits high total inequality, largely driven by within-country disparities, reflecting the concentration of funding in high-performing regions. Cohesion R&I shows lower total inequality overall, with a substantial share of variance between countries, in line with its redistributive mandate. When disaggregated by governance level, nationally managed Cohesion OPs concentrate funding in technologically advanced regions while maintaining limited within-country disparities, whereas regionally managed programmes exhibit greater intra-national inequality, reflecting competitive dynamics within fixed territorial envelopes. The descriptive evidence, therefore, already highlights the importance of disentangling governance effects in the subsequent econometric analysis.

Table 1. Theil index of per capita R&I funding by instrument and governance mode (2014–2020)

	Total	Between-country	Within-country
Full sample			
H2020 per capita	0.923	0.144	0.779
Cohesion R&I per capita	0.683	0.481	0.202
Group of countries			
Centrally-managed funds			
H2020 per capita	0.7465	0.1715	0.575
Cohesion R&I per capita	0.6026	0.4446	0.158
Decentrally-managed funds			
H2020 per capita	0.9229	0.1100	0.8129
Cohesion R&I per capita	0.5627	0.1203	0.4424

Note: The Theil index measures inequality in the distribution of R&I funding. A value of 0 indicates that every unit receives an identical per capita share (perfect balance), and as values move toward 1 (or higher), it indicates that funding is increasingly concentrated in fewer countries or regions. The between-country column shows how much inequality is driven by gaps between different countries, while within-country captures disparities within the national borders. Centrally-managed funds or national OP model comprises 21 countries: AT, BG, CZ, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, HR, HU, IT, LT, LU, LV, MT, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, and SK. Decentrally-managed funds or regional OP model focuses on 11 countries, namely BE, DE, EL, ES, FR, IE, IT, NL, PL, PT, and SE.

4. Methodological approach

To conduct the present analysis, we use a Spatial Autoregressive Combined (SAC) model to explain R&I funding intensity, measured in per capita terms and expressed in logarithmic form (1). This model captures both spatial lag and spatial error dependence, allowing us to account for the influence of neighbouring units on funding patterns while controlling for unobserved spatially correlated effects (LeSage & Pace, 2009). Equation (1) is indexed by region i , expressed at NUTS 3 level (2024 classification), and estimated using data from EU-26 Member States, with Cyprus excluded due to missing data.

$$y_i = \rho \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} y_j + \beta X_i' + \mu_i \quad (1)$$

$$\mu_i = \lambda \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} \mu_j + \epsilon_i$$

Where:

- y_i captures the logarithm of R&I funding per capita (Horizon 2020; Cohesion Policy; Cohesion Policy under a national or regional management of OPs);
- w_{ij} is (i,j)-th element of the row-standardised contiguity matrix W , where $w_{ij} = 1$ if two regions share a common border and 0 otherwise, and rows sum to one;
- ρ is the spatial lag parameter;
- λ is the spatial error parameter;
- X'_i refers to a set of explanatory variables reflecting the socio-economic characteristics of the regions;
- ϵ_i denotes an independently and identically distributed error term with zero mean and constant variance.

The dependent variable, y_i is measured separately for the two funding streams under analysis: per capita Horizon 2020 funding, and per capita R&I Cohesion Policy funding, with the latter further divided into sub-samples depending on whether funds are managed at the national or regional level.

Following the literature on economic geography (Asheim & Gertler, 2006; Feldman, 1999; Feldman & Kogler, 2010) and funding concentration (Bachtrögler-Unger et al., 2025; Dotti & Spithoven, 2018; Fitjar, 2025; A. Santos & Conte, 2024; Skupien & Rüffin, 2020), we include explanatory variables capturing regional endowments and agglomeration economies, namely:

- Knowledge stock measured by patent stock³ per capita;
- Level of development, proxied by Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita;
- Industrial structure captured by the contribution of the knowledge-intensive industry⁴ to the total Gross Value Added (GVA);
- Degree of urbanisation proxied by population density;
- Labour market dynamics measured by unemployment rate and old-age dependency ratio;
- Institutional quality and national innovation systems captured by country dummies.

³ Patent stock is estimated using the perpetual inventory method and a depreciation rate of 5 %, following (Cicerone et al., 2023). The stock is calculated using information from 1995 onwards. The value of patent stock is then divided by the number of inhabitants, expressed in millions.

⁴ Knowledge intensive services include economic activities classified in the NACE sections J, M and N.

We expect knowledge stock and GDP per capita to exert a positive effect on R&I funding intensity, reflecting both absorptive capacity and the structural link between innovation and regional wealth (Dotti & Spithoven, 2018; Fitjar, 2025). A higher share of knowledge-intensive industries and greater population density are also expected to be positively associated with funding, as they signal agglomeration economies and stronger innovation ecosystems (Bachtrögler-Unger et al., 2025). In contrast, higher unemployment and old-age dependency ratios may exert a negative effect, as they reflect structural weaknesses and lower innovation potential (Rodríguez-Pose & Crescenzi, 2008; Rodríguez-Pose & Wilkie, 2019).

Data on R&I Cohesion Policy funds were produced using information from the European Commission's Cohesion open data platform (see Appendix A for more details). Horizon data were retrieved using project data from the Horizon dashboard, patent data from OECD REG-PAT and socio-economic characteristics of the regions were obtained from the ARDECO dataset. R&I funding data refers to the total of EU spending during the programming period 2014-2020, and explanatory variables reflect the situation of the regions at the beginning of the programming period (2014) to reduce potential endogeneity and reverse causality bias. R&I funds and GDP are transformed in Purchasing Power Parity to allow comparison between regions.

Model selection was based on a comparative assessment of Spatial Autoregressive (SAR), Spatial Error (SEM), and SAC estimates, with the SAC model with country fixed effects consistently reporting the lowest AIC and BIC across both Horizon 2020 (Table C1 in Appendix C) and Cohesion Policy (Table C2 in Appendix C) model specifications. While a structural correlation between regional wealth (GDP per capita) and innovation output (Patent stock per capita) is expected, collinearity diagnostics confirm the stability of our estimates; the maximum VIF (4.48) and mean VIF (2.48) remain well below the conservative threshold of 10 (Table B2 in Appendix B). Furthermore, leave-one-out robustness checks (Table C3 in Appendix C), alternating the exclusion of GDP per capita and Patent stock, demonstrate that coefficients remain stable in sign and significance. This confirms that the model successfully distinguishes between the wealth effect and innovation capacity, with the full SAC specification providing the most robust framework.

5. Results

5.1. Determinants of the spatial distribution of R&I funding

Table 2 reports the results of the Spatial Autoregressive Combined (SAC) models showing some differences in the determinants of fund allocation between Horizon 2020 and the R&I component of Cohesion Policy during the 2014-2020 period, even after controlling for spatial dependence and baseline regional characteristics measured in 2014.

Table 2. Results of Spatial Autoregressive Combined (SAC) model, dependent variables: Horizon 2020 funds per capita (log) or R&I Cohesion Policy funds per capita (log)

Variables	Horizon 2020 (1)	R&I Cohesion Policy (2)
Patent stock per capita, log	0.483*** (0.0527)	0.0871** (0.0378)
GDP per capita, log	1.581*** (0.160)	0.680*** (0.111)
Share GVA from KIS industry	5.608*** (1.060)	-3.186*** (0.772)
Old-age dependency ratio	-0.0212*** (0.00792)	-0.0254*** (0.00596)
Unemployment rate	0.0171 (0.0152)	0.0581*** (0.0127)
Population density, log	0.284*** (0.0477)	0.0416 (0.0371)
Country fixed effects	Yes	Yes
Y	-0.140*** (0.0510)	-0.119** (0.0492)
e.Y	0.343*** (0.0558)	0.764*** (0.0286)
var(e.Y)	1.297*** (0.0589)	0.650*** (0.0377)
Constant	No	No
Observations	1,164	1,164
Log Pseudolikelihood	-1,819.7	-1,495.0
Pseudo R2	0.5473	0.5086
Wald Test (Prob > chi2)	0.0000	0.0000
AIC	3,709.4	3,060.1
BIC	3,886.5	3,237.2

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. Significance level: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

The H2020 model in column (1) provides strong evidence of a cumulative advantage dynamic (Dotti & Spithoven, 2018; A. Santos & Conte, 2024). The coefficients for initial economic development (GDP per capita) and technological specialisation (patent stock per capita) are both positive and highly significant. This suggests that H2020 funds are heavily concentrated in regions that already own high levels of human capital and innovation output. This pattern aligns with previous evidence showing that participation in Framework Programmes is strongly associated with pre-existing scientific capacity and technological specialization (Dotti & Spithoven, 2018; Piro et al., 2024), reinforcing the view that excellence-driven schemes tend to reward established innovation systems. Furthermore, the positive relationship of knowledge-intensive services and population density confirms that H2020 operates under an agglomeration logic, favoring urban hubs of excellence where R&I ecosystems are usually most mature (Feldman & Kogler, 2010; Rodríguez-Pose & Crescenzi, 2008).

In contrast, the results for R&I Cohesion Policy in column (2) describe a comparatively more redistributive or compensatory allocation logic, despite the positive relationship with the level of development and pre-innovation capacity; however, in both their marginal effects⁵ display a lower magnitude than the H2020 model.⁶ This difference is particularly visible for GDP per capita, whose marginal effect is three times lower for R&I Cohesion Policy than for Horizon, suggesting that, although more developed regions are not excluded, economic prosperity is a substantially weaker predictor of Cohesion R&I allocations than in the excellence-oriented H2020 scheme.

Interestingly, the negative and significant coefficient for knowledge-intensive services indicates that regions less specialized in service-based innovation structures receive comparatively higher Cohesion R&I support. This finding is consistent with the place-based rationale of Cohesion Policy and with evidence that Cohesion Policy funds are more likely to flow toward structurally weaker territories (Mieszkowski & Barbero, 2021; A. Santos & Conte, 2024), such as lagging industrial or agricultural regions rather than established high-tech service hubs. Moreover, the positive association with unemployment rates suggests that socio-economic vulnerability is embedded in the allocation logic of Cohesion R&I funding, reinforcing its convergence-oriented mandate. In contrast to H2020, where

⁵ The marginal effect is obtained by multiplying the estimated coefficient by the ratio of the mean of the dependent variable to the mean of the independent variable.

⁶ Patent Stock with a marginal effect of 0.0042 for Horizon fundings versus 0.0033 for R&I Cohesion Policy ones; GDP per capita with 27,585 for Horizon versus 9,171 for R&I Cohesion Policy.

market-driven and excellence criteria dominate, Cohesion R&I appears to integrate broader territorial development objectives.

The negative and significant spatial lag across both funding streams suggests a competitive or “crowding out” effect. This is consistent with the concentration of research excellence in specific metropolitan hubs that may reduce access to funding in adjacent NUTS3 territories (Feldman & Kogler, 2010). In the case of Cohesion Policy, this competition is further intensified by administrative structures, because funding envelopes are defined at the NUTS2 level, NUTS3 regions within the same territory effectively compete for a finite amount of resources.

5.2. Territorial heterogeneity across groups

To complement the previous analysis, we divided the regions into groups. Firstly, we applied the Cohesion criteria classification (less developed, transition and more developed regions) to all NUTS3-level regions within a NUTS2-level category (Table 3). Secondly, regions were grouped based on their geographical location: Southern, Central, Eastern and Northern Europe (Table 4). The analysis of the Table 3 and Table 4 reveals that the EU-wide averages reported in Table 2 mask internal heterogeneity.

Across all three Cohesion categories under H2020 funding, the coefficients for most of the drivers are quite consistent (columns (1), (3) and (5) in Table 3), confirming that the excellence-based logic identified at the EU average level also holds within each group. In particular, patent stock, GDP per capita and the share of knowledge-intensive services remain positive and significant across all categories, reinforcing the idea that H2020 primarily rewards existing scientific and economic capacity. However, the most interesting differences are in these models are the spatial components. The spatial lag is positive and significant for transition regions but negative for less developed regions, while for more developed regions it’s insignificant. This might indicate that in transition regions, neighboring regions’ H2020 intensity has a strong local impact (spillovers), while in less developed regions, the spatial dependence is negative, suggesting at potential competitive effects or limited absorption capacity.

In turn, the differences across region typology are slightly more pronounced for the estimates in the models explaining R&I Cohesion Policy funding (columns (2), (4) and (6) in Table 4). For instance, patent stock is only a significant driver in less developed and transition regions, whereas higher GDP per capita explains funding in transition and more developed regions only.

Table 3. Results of SAC model by Cohesion region category, dependent variables: Horizon 2020 (H2020) funds per capita (log) or R&I Cohesion Policy (CP) funds per capita (log)

Variables	Less developed regions		Transition regions		More developed regions	
	H2020 (1)	R&I CP (2)	H2020 (3)	R&I CP (4)	H2020 (5)	R&I CP (6)
Patent stock per capita, log	0.571*** (0.0909)	0.214*** (0.0511)	0.413*** (0.114)	0.177** (0.0865)	0.458*** (0.0756)	-0.0301 (0.0554)
GDP per capita, log	1.078*** (0.329)	-0.127 (0.190)	2.115*** (0.604)	1.139*** (0.413)	1.828*** (0.196)	0.783*** (0.134)
Share GVA from KIS industry	11.39*** (2.861)	3.124** (1.589)	11.31** (5.101)	1.692 (3.655)	4.364*** (1.199)	-2.960*** (0.897)
Old-age dependency ratio	-0.000206 (0.0120)	-0.0108 (0.00713)	-0.00872 (0.0200)	-0.0268 (0.0176)	-0.0404*** (0.0111)	-0.0269*** (0.00836)
Unemployment rate	-0.0326 (0.0223)	0.0263** (0.0133)	0.0540 (0.0419)	0.102** (0.0438)	0.0692** (0.0322)	0.0304 (0.0260)
Population density, log	0.241*** (0.0884)	-0.150*** (0.0522)	0.315*** (0.112)	0.150 (0.0948)	0.179*** (0.0623)	0.0651 (0.0502)
Country fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Y	-0.232** (0.100)	0.173** (0.0834)	0.281*** (0.101)	-0.0443 (0.0904)	0.0205 (0.0624)	-0.0990 (0.0758)
e.Y	0.160 (0.119)	0.414*** (0.0968)	-0.256* (0.143)	0.583*** (0.0777)	0.184** (0.0787)	0.675*** (0.0489)
var(e.Y)	0.829*** (0.0662)	0.268*** (0.0475)	1.432*** (0.148)	0.756*** (0.0903)	1.324*** (0.0768)	0.659*** (0.0451)
Constant	No	No	No	No	No	No
Observations	296	296	200	200	668	668
Log Pseudolikelihood	-394.90	-232.97	-323.90	-267.86	-1044.09	-851.08
Pseudo R2	0.6388	0.6843	0.3909	0.3353	0.5395	0.4366
Wald Test (Prob > chi2)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
AIC	839.81	515.94	685.80	573.72	2,146.2	1,760.2
BIC	932.06	608.20	748.47	636.39	2,276.8	1,890.8

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. Significance level: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

Table 4. Results of SAC model by European geographic region, dependent variables: Horizon 2020 (H2020) funds per capita (log) or R&I Cohesion Policy (CP) funds per capita (log)

Variables	Southern European regions		Central European regions		Eastern European regions		Northern European regions	
	H2020 (1)	R&I CP (2)	H2020 (3)	R&I CP (4)	H2020 (5)	R&I CP (6)	H2020 (7)	R&I CP (8)
Patent stock per capita, log	0.381*** (0.0857)	0.203*** (0.0499)	0.539*** (0.0817)	0.123* (0.0638)	0.583*** (0.126)	0.0487 (0.0430)	0.841*** (0.113)	0.0273 (0.0644)
GDP per capita, log	0.621 (0.402)	-0.156 (0.264)	1.461*** (0.214)	0.575*** (0.156)	0.520 (0.388)	0.00224 (0.139)	1.395*** (0.368)	0.592** (0.266)
Share GVA from KIS industry	18.78*** (2.857)	4.381** (1.760)	3.719*** (1.346)	-3.295*** (1.050)	8.964*** (2.769)	0.0758 (1.012)	9.152*** (2.657)	0.842 (1.868)
Old-age dependency ratio	-0.0297** (0.0129)	-0.00307 (0.00990)	-0.0324*** (0.0110)	-0.0442*** (0.00853)	-0.0169 (0.0193)	0.00180 (0.00733)	-0.0530*** (0.0173)	-0.0102 (0.0112)
Unemployment rate	-0.00704 (0.0164)	0.0439*** (0.0129)	0.0616* (0.0322)	0.0166 (0.0291)	-0.0410 (0.0328)	0.00528 (0.0128)	0.407*** (0.0732)	0.160*** (0.0565)
Population density, log	-0.0157 (0.0709)	-0.189*** (0.0547)	0.412*** (0.0711)	0.162*** (0.0574)	0.341** (0.135)	-0.0260 (0.0470)	-0.521*** (0.0701)	-0.469*** (0.0757)
Country fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Y	0.248*** (0.0608)	-0.0109 (0.0480)	-0.361*** (0.0827)	-0.464*** (0.0780)	-0.301** (0.144)	-0.0830 (0.271)	-0.0229 (0.0674)	0.0741 (0.0689)
e.Y	-0.363*** (0.111)	0.687*** (0.0525)	0.493*** (0.0719)	0.880*** (0.0260)	0.231 (0.161)	0.484** (0.214)	-0.691*** (0.147)	0.437*** (0.125)
var(e.Y)	1.106*** (0.0987)	0.391*** (0.0528)	1.354*** (0.0834)	0.769*** (0.0572)	0.712*** (0.0729)	0.0882*** (0.0327)	0.324*** (0.0456)	0.135*** (0.0259)
Constant	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Observations	279	279	635	635	171	171	79	79
Log Pseudolikelihood	-415.72	-284.28	-1,021.0	-901.48	-216.1	-39.86	-72.4	-35.19
Pseudo R2	0.5678	0.5127	0.4934	0.1126	0.6708	0.8123	0.8285	0.8982
Wald Test (Prob > chi2)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
AIC	863.45	600.56	2,074.0	1,835.0	460.2	107.7	176.8	102.4
BIC	921.55	658.66	2,145.3	1,906.2	504.1	151.7	214.7	140.3

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. Significance level: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$. Northern (DK, EE, FI, IE, LT, LV, SE); Southern (CY, EL, HR, IT, MT, PT, ES, SI); Eastern (BG, PL, RO, SK, HU); and Central/Western (AT, BE, CZ, DE, FR, LU, NL).

The coefficient for the share of knowledge-intensive services changes from negative in the EU-wide estimation to positive in model for less developed regions model, whereas the spatial lag is positive (while it is negative in the EU-wide estimation). This suggests that, in less developed regions, Cohesion R&I funding may reinforce emerging knowledge hubs rather than compensating for structurally weaker territories within that group.

The geographic disaggregation in Table 3 reveals further asymmetries. For H2020, the excellence logic generally remains within each geographical country group, with a positive and significant patent stock and the share of knowledge services across Southern, Central, Eastern, and Northern Europe, confirming the centrality of technological capacity. The most substantial difference lies in the spatial lag. H2020 exhibits positive spatial lag dependence in Southern Europe but negative lag effects in Central and Northern Europe, indicating that the nature of interregional interaction (positive spillovers versus competitive effect) differs across macro-regions. This may reflect stronger cross-regional research collaboration and clustering dynamics in Southern Europe. In contrast, the presence of multiple highly competitive regions in Central and Northern Europe could generate substitution or crowding-out effects.

For R&I Cohesion Policy, substantial differences emerge mainly within Southern European regions, with funding being more concentrated in areas with knowledge-intensive services and patent activity, however, with a distributive logic (by still targeting less populated regions and with higher unemployment). This combination suggests a hybrid allocation pattern in Southern Europe, where Cohesion funds simultaneously support structurally weaker labour markets and reinforce pre-existing knowledge capacities. This may reflect administrative concentration of absorptive capacity in a limited number of regional hubs. In Eastern European regions, despite the high R-square, almost all the variables are non-significant, except for the spatial error. Given that regions in this geographical location received a relatively homogeneous amount of funding, this may imply that allocation is driven less by observable structural characteristics and more by country-level programming frameworks or nationally coordinated investment strategies.

5.3. Spatial distribution of R&I Cohesion Policy funding by governance model

To reply to the second research question of the paper, Table 5 provides the SAC estimates for subsets of countries categorised by the governance structure of R&I Cohesion Policy: centrally managed

(column 1) and regionally managed (columns 2-3). Column (3) further refines the decentralised model by introducing a dummy variable that distinguishes between macro-regional (NUTS1) and regional (NUTS2) management levels.

Table 5. Results of Spatial Autoregressive Combined (SAC) model, dependent variables: R&I Cohesion Policy funds per capita (log) by governance model

Variables	National OP	Regional OP	
	(1)	(2)	(3)
Patent stock per capita, log	0.194*** (0.0555)	0.125*** (0.0462)	0.125*** (0.0462)
GDP per capita, log	-0.0981 (0.224)	0.670*** (0.124)	0.670*** (0.124)
Share GVA from KIS industry	-0.909 (1.600)	-2.129** (0.895)	-2.129** (0.895)
Old-age dependency ratio	0.0142 (0.0100)	-0.0444*** (0.00692)	-0.0444*** (0.00692)
Unemployment rate	0.0329** (0.0155)	0.0476*** (0.0149)	0.0476*** (0.0149)
Population density, log	-0.0536 (0.0577)	-0.0428 (0.0412)	-0.0428 (0.0412)
NUTS1 vs NUTS2 management	- -	- -	-0.237 (1.568)
Country fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes
Y	0.112* (0.0619)	-0.352*** (0.0643)	-0.352*** (0.0643)
e.Y	0.596*** (0.0570)	0.864*** (0.0219)	0.864*** (0.0219)
var(e.Y)	0.777*** (0.0923)	0.706*** (0.0478)	0.706*** (0.0478)
Constant	No	No	No
Observations	571	931	931
Log Pseudolikelihood	-765.5	-1,278.1	-1,278.1
Pseudo R2	0.6313	0.0534	0.0534
Wald Test (Prob > chi2)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
AIC	1,590.9	2,596.1	2,596.1
BIC	1,721.3	2,692.8	2,692.8

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. Significance level: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1. The National OP model comprises 21 countries: AT, BG, CZ, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, HR, HU, IT, LT, LU, LV, MT, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, and SK. The Regional OP model focuses on 11 countries, namely BE, DE, EL, ES, FR, IE, IT, NL, PL, PT, and SE.

This disaggregation enables us to evaluate whether the level at which Cohesion R&I funds are administered systematically influences their spatial allocation patterns. The results reveal a clear divergence in the allocation logic depending on the OP governance level, suggesting that the spatial concentration dynamics are not only programme-specific (H2020 versus Cohesion), but also mediated by a multi-level governance within Cohesion Policy itself.

In the nationally managed model (column 1), allocation appears to be strongly aligned with pre-existing innovation capacity. Patent intensity remains the most robust predictor, while GDP per capita plays a more limited role. This indicates that technological specialisation, rather than general prosperity, drives selection, reflecting the excellence-oriented approach observed in Framework Programmes (Dotti & Spithoven, 2018; Piro et al., 2024). National OP allocations thus appear to prioritise territorially concentrated “hubs of excellence”, thereby reinforcing mechanisms of cumulative advantage similar to those identified in competitive funding schemes. This also aligns with Santos and Conte’s (2024) findings regarding the Recovery and Resilience Facility funds in Portugal. In contrast to the EU-wide results, the spatial dependence is positive and significant, indicating that funding patterns under national OP generate positive spillovers, whereas regional OP negative ones reports negative ones, in line with the reasoning of competitive allocation within fixed regional envelopes.

Disaggregating decentralised systems by governance level (macro-regional NUTS1 vs regional NUTS2) also reveals important heterogeneity in allocation patterns. Table 6 reports SAC estimates including interaction terms between the governance-level dummy (NUTS1 vs NUTS2) and the explanatory variables, allowing the determinants of allocation to vary systematically by management level. When programmes are managed at the NUTS1 level, wealth, patent intensity, and urbanisation remain significant drivers, indicating a strategic selection of territorially competitive nodes. In contrast, under NUTS2 management, GDP per capita and patent stock lose statistical significance, while funding is more likely to flow toward less densely populated areas and territories with a lower share of knowledge-intensive services. These findings suggest that NUTS1 authorities behave similarly to national-level ones, prioritising competitive regional champions, whereas NUTS2 authorities appear more aligned with the place-based logic. However, both sub-national governance level maintains a positive association with unemployment, indicating that socio-economic vulnerability remains an allocation criterion regardless of management level.

Table 6. Results of Spatial Autoregressive Combined (SAC) model, dependent variables: R&I Cohesion Policy funds per capita (log) under Regional OP

Variables	Variable included in the interaction term:					
	Patent stock per capita, log (1)	GDP per capita, log (2)	Share GVA from KIS industry (3)	Old-age dependency ratio (4)	Unemployment rate (5)	Population density, log (6)
Interaction term: Var # level of governance Regional OP						
NUTS2	0.0911 (0.0585)	-0.0366 (0.225)	-4.577*** (1.236)	-0.0212** (0.00889)	0.0424*** (0.0163)	-0.261*** (0.0500)
NUTS1	0.171** (0.0670)	0.878*** (0.135)	0.00699 (1.160)	-0.0724*** (0.00974)	0.0792** (0.0344)	0.220*** (0.0536)
Other control variables	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Y	-0.359*** (0.0642)	-0.358*** (0.0635)	-0.365*** (0.0635)	-0.316*** (0.0649)	-0.337*** (0.0648)	-0.386*** (0.0617)
e.Y	0.868*** (0.0213)	0.872*** (0.0207)	0.871*** (0.0209)	0.854*** (0.0234)	0.856*** (0.0230)	0.879*** (0.0194)
var(e.Y)	0.702*** (0.0478)	0.690*** (0.0461)	0.694*** (0.0467)	0.703*** (0.0471)	0.712*** (0.0480)	0.656*** (0.0422)
Constant	No	No	No	No	No	No
Observations	931	931	931	931	931	931
Log Pseudolikelihood	-1,277.6	-1,271.3	-1,274.1	-1,269.7	-1,277.6	-1,252.5
Pseudo R2	0.0432	0.0441	0.0419	0.0836	0.0737	0.0712
Wald Test (Prob > chi2)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
AIC	2,597.3	2,584.5	2,590.1	2,581.5	2,597.3	2,547.1
BIC	2,698.8	2,686.1	2,691.7	2,683.1	2,698.8	2,648.7
Z-test: NUTS2 versus NUTS1	0.369	0.000	0.007	0.000	0.334	0.000

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. Significance level: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$. The Regional OP model focuses on 11 countries, namely Belgium (BE), Germany (DE), Greece (EL), Spain (ES), France (FR), Ireland (IE), Italy (IT), the Netherlands (NL), Poland (PL), Portugal (PT), and Sweden (SE).

Across all decentralised configurations, the persistence of a negative spatial lag signals competitive territorial dynamics within limited financial envelopes. Even where allocation appears more place-sensitive (NUTS2), inter-regional coordination mechanisms seem insufficient to counteract competitive pressures, limiting the emergence of integrated regional innovation systems

6. Conclusion

By comparing two contrasting intervention logics within a unified empirical framework, using the same set of regional socio-economic indicators across identical NUTS3 regions, this study provides new insights into how institutional design and regional characteristics interact to shape the geography of EU research and innovation funding. Horizon 2020 prioritises excellence, concentrating resources in established innovation hubs and reinforcing cumulative advantage, which tend to increase territorial disparities. In contrast, R&I Cohesion Policy follows a more redistributive and convergence-oriented logic at sub-regional level, in line with its mandate, targeting socio-economically vulnerable and structurally weaker regions, while still reflecting some sensitivity to development and innovation capacity. Importantly, the results do not indicate that Cohesion Policy has systematically converged towards a pure excellence-based allocation logic when looking at sub-regional level, even if elements of concentration are observable in specific contexts.

Disaggregated analyses reveal further heterogeneity. While H2020 displays a territorially consistent excellence-driven logic across Europe, Cohesion R&I funding is context-dependent, influenced by regional development levels, macro-geographical patterns, and governance structures. Spatial dependence is consistently observed, often negative, indicating competitive dynamics between neighbouring regions, though positive spillovers emerge for H2020 among transition regions and Southern Europe, and for Cohesion policy among less developed regions. Competition between neighbouring regions is particularly strong in Central and Eastern Europe under Horizon.

Governance scale mediates these patterns within Cohesion R&I. Nationally managed programmes are more sensitive to technological specialisation and generate positive spillovers, suggesting coordinated clustering dynamics. Regionally managed programmes, by contrast, exhibit stronger intra-territorial competition and a closer link to regional income levels, reflecting a more place-sensitive but competitive allocation logic.

EU R&I funding instruments and governance arrangements generate distinct spatial patterns, each embodying trade-offs between efficiency, redistribution, and spatial coordination. Horizon 2020 concentrates resources to maximise excellence but at the cost of internal inequality, while Cohesion R&I promotes cross-country redistribution and addresses vulnerability, though internal disparities vary with governance. National Cohesion programmes combine hub concentration with positive spillovers, whereas regional programmes distribute funding more widely but increase competition. No single model simultaneously maximises excellence, cohesion, and spatial coordination; rather, instrument design and governance scale define the balance between concentrating resources in high-performing areas and supporting territorial convergence.

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Appendix

Appendix A. Data source and construction

Data at the NUTS3-level on EU funds under the 2014-2020 Cohesion Policy for Thematic Objective 1 (Research and Innovation) are estimated using data from the European Commission’s Cohesion Open Data Platform, specifically the dataset “ESIF 2014-2020 categorisation ERDF-ESF-CF planned vs implemented”.⁷ This dataset provides information on the geographical distribution of EU-eligible costs of selected/decided projects by their territorial coverage at the end of 2023. Thematic objective 1 (TO01) is funded mainly by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), one of the four funds supporting the 2014-2020 Cohesion policy, the others are European Social Fund, Cohesion Fund and Youth Employment Initiative.⁸ Within ERDF, the dataset also included information on funded managed under territorial cooperation programmes, which are also included under the present analysis.

As described in Table A1, information about the territorial dimension of the funds is not available on a single scale. It is divided by their geographical coverage of the projects: NUTS3-, NUTS2-, NUTS1- or country-level data. This means that when a project has a social impact at the country-level, benefiting the population of the entire country, its geographical coverage is the country; when it is an NUTS3 region, it is encoded as such.

Table A1. Geographical distribution of EU-eligible costs under Thematic Objective 1 (Research and Innovation): raw data, cumulative by 2023, EU27

Geographical coverage	Share EU in eligible costs (project decided)	
	EUR	% Total
Country	4,591,858,409	9%
NUTS1	1,252,730,842	3%
NUTS2	20,813,135,671	42%
NUTS3	22,456,449,873	46%
TOTAL	49,114,174,794	100%

Source: Own elaboration based on data from the European Commission’s Cohesion Open Data Platform - “ESIF 2014-2020 categorisation ERDF-ESF-CF planned vs implemented”.

⁷ Last updated data on 6 April 2024.

⁸ For the 2021-2027 EU budget, the Youth Employment Initiative was integrated into the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+), whereas in the 2014-2020 period, it was a distinct initiative that ran alongside the European Social Fund.

Under the previous assumption, we can see that only 46% of the total eligible cost is available at the NUTS 3 level. The remaining is reported at more aggregated levels: 42% at NUTS 2-, 3% at NUTS 1-, and 9% at the country-level. Following Marques Santos et al. (2023), we regionalise expenditures reported at higher territorial levels by allocating them to NUTS 3 regions proportionally to their population shares. This approach is consistent with the logic of Cohesion Policy, as 42% of the data are reported at NUTS2-level, where budget allocations are largely structured around this typology of regions and their population size, particularly within the classification of more developed, transition, and less developed regions. Furthermore, using population to regionalise is also a common approach, used by the European Commission⁹, when there is no better data about where funding was actually spent. Data on population refers to the average between 2014 and 2020, estimated using ARDECO [SNPTD]. Importantly, when a location (NUTS3-, NUTS2- or NUTS1-level) in the raw dataset is available at the NUTS classification different from the 2024 version, we use the European Commission NUTS converter before the regionalisation.

Following Marques Santos et al. (2023), EU-eligible costs grouped under Multi-TOs are allocated across individual TOs according to the classification of their priority axes. Using data from the planned ESIF 2014-2020 financial allocations, we calculated the share of the EU budget assigned to each TO within the total amount of each priority axis code, at the level of each OP. These estimated shares, based on planned amounts, are then applied to the Multi-TO categories to distribute their financial amounts across the respective TOs, and to isolate the share imputed to TO01.

To divide R&I funds by the management level of operational programmes (OPs), we follow Santos et al. (2025), who classify OPs as either centralised (nationally managed) or decentralised (regionally managed) based on the geographical scope indicated in the programme title. If the title includes the name of a specific region (at the NUTS 1 or NUTS 2 level), the OP is considered regional and therefore decentralised. If no regional name appears in the title, the programme is classified as national, implying centralised governance. To determine whether a regional OP corresponds to a NUTS 1 or NUTS 2 region, we rely on the Eurostat correspondence tables that match region names with NUTS codes. While R&I funding under territorial cooperation programmes is included in the R&I Cohesion Policy dataset, these programmes are excluded from the governance split. The classification into centralised and decentralised applies only to national and regional OPs.

⁹ See e.g. the methodological approach designed by Ciffolilli et al. (2015) for the geography of expenditure of 2007-2013 ERDF and CF, integrated in the Historic EU payments annual time series produced by the European Commission.

Appendix B. Descriptive statistics and multicollinearity analysis

Table B1. R&I funding per capita by region category

Category	H2020 per capita	R&I Cohesion policy per capita		
		Total	National OP	Regional OP
More developed	168.7	60.0	26.5	30.0
Transition	40.1	145.2	49.0	91.3
Less developed	35.6	327.2	282.0	43.2
EU	115.8	144.3	99.6	41.4

Note: Region category refers to 2014-2020 Cohesion policy classification.

Table B2. Correlation matrix and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Variables	VIF	Correlation matrix				
		1	2	3	4	5 6
1 Patent stock per capita, log	4.48	1				
2 GDP per capita, log	3.50	0.836	1			
3 Share GVA from KIS industry	2.11	0.592	0.567	1		
4 Old-age dependency ratio	1.32	0.094	0.123	-0.135	1	
5 Unemployment rate	1.71	-0.556	-0.384	-0.363	0.054	1
6 Population density, log	1.76	0.385	0.440	0.599	-0.324	-0.244 1
Mean VIF	2.48					

Table B3. Descriptive statistics: mean, maximum and minimum

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
Horizon 2020 per capita, log	1,164	2.79	1.74	0	7.82
Cohesion R&I per capita, log	1,164	3.79	1.63	0	7.51
Cohesion R&I per capita - National OP, log	571	4.11	1.84	0	7.25
Cohesion R&I per capita - Regional OP, log	931	3.08	1.41	0	7.51
Patent stock per capita, log	1,164	6.00	1.77	1.08	10.1
GDP per capita, log	1,164	10.0	0.64	8.03	11.9
Share GVA from KIS industry	1,164	0.11	0.05	0.02	0.47
Old-age dependency ratio	1,164	66.64	7.63	43	133
Unemployment rate	1,164	9.63	6.84	2.4	34.8
Population density, log	1,164	5.01	1.28	0.61	9.96

Appendix C. Sensitivity analysis

Table C1. Results of Spatial Autoregressive Combined (SAC), Spatial Error (SEM), and Spatial Spatial Autoregressive (SAR) model, dependent variables: Horizon 2020 funds per capita (log) – Selection of spatial model

Variables	SAC (1)	SEM (2)	SEM (3)	SAR (4)	SAR (5)
Patent stock per capita, log	0.437*** (0.0469)	0.429*** (0.0513)	0.304*** (0.0510)	0.364*** (0.0512)	0.0917* (0.0486)
GDP per capita, log	1.115*** (0.128)	1.624*** (0.161)	0.930*** (0.133)	1.641*** (0.163)	0.738*** (0.122)
Share GVA from KIS industry	4.454*** (1.015)	5.239*** (1.044)	5.443*** (1.148)	5.039*** (1.019)	5.870*** (1.090)
Old-age dependency ratio	-0.0348*** (0.00673)	-0.0227*** (0.00778)	-0.0422*** (0.00707)	-0.0228*** (0.00748)	-0.0335*** (0.00587)
Unemployment rate	-0.0211* (0.0118)	0.0260* (0.0143)	0.0350*** (0.0104)	0.0294** (0.0135)	0.0539*** (0.00726)
Population density, log	0.368*** (0.0476)	0.259*** (0.0462)	0.312*** (0.0507)	0.236*** (0.0439)	0.153*** (0.0427)
Country fixed effects	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Y	-0.553*** (0.0452)	-	-	0.0576* (0.0328)	0.265*** (0.0331)
e.Y	0.834*** (0.0202)	0.205*** (0.0412)	0.585*** (0.0295)	-	-
var(e.Y)	1.183*** (0.0586)	1.331*** (0.0586)	1.569*** (0.0689)	1.360*** (0.0596)	1.860*** (0.0726)
Constant	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Observations	1,164	1,164	1,164	1,164	1,164
Log Pseudolikelihood	-1,901.5	-1,823.0	-1,961.1	-1,830.8	-2,021.2
Pseudo R2	0.3184	0.5469	0.3126	0.5461	0.3095
Wald Test (Prob > chi2)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0791	0.0000
AIC	3,822.9	3,714.0	3,940.2	3,729.6	4,060.4
BIC	3,873.5	3,886.0	3,985.7	3,901.6	4,105.9

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. Significance level: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$. In specifications with country fixed effects, the constant term is omitted to avoid perfect multicollinearity.

Table C2. Results of Spatial Autoregressive Combined (SAC), Spatial Error (SEM), and Spatial Autoregressive (SAR) model, dependent variables: R&I Cohesion policy funds per capita (log) – Selection of spatial model

Variables	SAC (1)	SEM (2)	SEM (3)	SAR (4)	SAR (5)
Patent stock per capita, log	0.0306 (0.0353)	0.0698* (0.0383)	-0.0236 (0.0371)	-0.0794** (0.0393)	-0.173*** (0.0344)
GDP per capita, log	0.335*** (0.0966)	0.695*** (0.113)	0.244** (0.100)	0.622*** (0.127)	0.200** (0.0886)
Share GVA from KIS industry	-3.470*** (0.748)	-3.368*** (0.786)	-3.522*** (0.805)	-4.316*** (0.793)	-2.875*** (0.782)
Old-age dependency ratio	-0.0416*** (0.00507)	-0.0258*** (0.00603)	-0.0469*** (0.00530)	-0.0233*** (0.00586)	-0.0392*** (0.00433)
Unemployment rate	0.0220** (0.00962)	0.0643*** (0.0125)	0.0353*** (0.00884)	0.0703*** (0.0106)	0.0347*** (0.00524)
Population density, log	0.103*** (0.0357)	0.0411 (0.0374)	0.0980*** (0.0376)	0.0435 (0.0343)	0.0218 (0.0306)
Country fixed effects	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Y	-0.375*** (0.0535)	-	-	0.415*** (0.0246)	0.554*** (0.0219)
e.Y	0.919*** (0.0127)	0.693*** (0.0246)	0.801*** (0.0186)	-	-
var(e.Y)	0.649*** (0.0396)	0.677*** (0.0377)	0.749*** (0.0412)	0.836*** (0.0451)	0.962*** (0.0484)
Constant	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Observations	1,164	1,164	1,164	1,164	1,164
Log Pseudolikelihood	-1,580.1	-1,496.6	-1,588.8	-1,568.9	-1,670.9
Pseudo R2	0.0124	0.5377	0.1473	0.5786	0.3677
Wald Test (Prob > chi2)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
AIC	3,180.2	3,061.2	3,195.6	3,205.8	3,359.8
BIC	3,230.8	3,233.2	3,241.2	3,377.8	3,405.3

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. Significance level: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1. In specifications with country fixed effects, the constant term is omitted to avoid perfect multicollinearity.

Table C3. Results of Spatial Autoregressive Combined (SAC) model, dependent variables: Horizon 2020 funds per capita (log) or R&I Cohesion policy funds per capita (log) – sensitivity analysis

Variables	Horizon 2020 per capita, log		Cohesion R&I per capita, log	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Patent stock per capita, log	-	0.578***	-	0.113***
	-	(0.0536)	-	(0.0383)
GDP per capita, log	1.889***	-	0.714***	-
	(0.163)	-	(0.111)	-
Share GVA from KIS industry	7.224***	6.181***	-2.832***	-3.113***
	(1.051)	(1.100)	(0.757)	(0.788)
Old-age dependency ratio	-0.0256***	-0.0399***	-0.0268***	-0.0343***
	(0.00781)	(0.00803)	(0.00597)	(0.00589)
Unemployment rate	-0.00886	-0.0255*	0.0548***	0.0454***
	(0.0138)	(0.0153)	(0.0125)	(0.0127)
Population density, log	0.263***	0.475***	0.0439	0.140***
	(0.0463)	(0.0459)	(0.0373)	(0.0339)
Country fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Y	0.0386	-0.167***	-0.0770	-0.114**
	(0.0513)	(0.0531)	(0.0480)	(0.0493)
e.Y	0.0911	0.368***	0.737***	0.747***
	(0.0664)	(0.0558)	(0.0307)	(0.0301)
var(e.Y)	1.417***	1.399***	0.664***	0.678***
	(0.0614)	(0.0647)	(0.0383)	(0.0392)
Constant	No	No	No	No
Observations	1,164	1,164	1,164	1,164
Log Pseudolikelihood	-1,855.6	-1,867.0	-1,497.5	-1,513.6
Pseudo R2	0.5266	0.5085	0.5252	0.5081
Wald Test (Prob > chi2)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
AIC	3,779.2	3,801.9	3,063.1	3,095.1
BIC	3,951.2	3,973.9	3,235.1	3,267.1

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. Significance level: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.